

DIRECT AND INDIRECT TRANSLATION STRATEGIES IN “DICK WHITTINGTON AND HIS CAT”

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In the research, I analyze the direct and indirect translation strategies used in rendering phraseological units from the English folktale “Dick Whittington and his cat” into Romanian. The present analysis is grounded in the translation procedures formulated by Jean-Paul Vinay and Jean Darbelnet in their work “*Stylistique comparée du français et de l’anglais*” / “Comparative Stylistics of French and English” (1958/1995). These procedures are commonly grouped into direct strategies and indirect strategies. The conclusions will verify whether indirect strategies are prevalent in the English–Romanian translation due to the typological distance between English (a Germanic language) and Romanian (a Romance language).